

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF BANKING INDUSTRY IN BANGLADESH

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate the relationship between four corporate governance mechanisms (board size, board independent director, chief executive officer duality and board audit committee) and financial performance of banking industry in order to identify whether or not bank's profitability is positively associated with its corporate governance disclosure level. The two financial ratios i.e., return on asset (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) are used to measure the financial performance. The study is based on the sample of listed conventional private commercial banks in Bangladesh selecting on the basis of a number of criterion. A linear regression analysis is used to analyze data and to test the hypotheses. Empirical results indicate that Board Independent Director has a positive relationship with ROA but positive significant relationship with ROE. Board Size has a positive relationship with ROA but negatively correlated with ROE. On the contrary, Board Audit Committee has negative relationship with both ROA and ROE. All the banks properly maintain the rules of BSEC regarding CEO duality.

Key words: Corporate governance, financial performance, return on asset (ROA) and return on equity (ROE).

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the Study

At present corporate governance is the burning issue in the business world. Good governance is one of the crucial conditions for the success of a nation and economy. In the same sense, good corporate governance is one of the prerequisite to maintain sustainable business sector development. Corporate governance refers to the rules, processes, or laws by which corporations are operated, regulated and controlled. Corporate governance also includes the relationships among the many stakeholders involved and the goals for which the corporation is governed. The principal stakeholders are the shareholders, board of directors, management committee, executive committee, audit committee and other stakeholders including labor or employees, customers, creditors, suppliers, regulators, and the community at large. Fairness, accountability, responsibility, transparency and integrity are the components of good corporate governance.

Generally development of business sector is measured by financial performance. It has been observed that indicators of financial performance and corporate governance are interrelated and good corporate governance has a positive effect on the performance. In Bangladesh, a lot of studies have already been conducted on the causal effect of the performances of the listed companies on the corporate governance in those companies. The studies of Shobod, Saiful, and Anup (2015); Rouf (2012); Omar et al.(2007), Samaduzzaman, Fazluz and Zaman (2015), Homayara et al. (2008), Rashid et al. (2010) have undertaken on the state of corporate governance of the companies listed with Dhaka Stock Exchange and Chittagong Stock Exchange to explain that corporate governance has a positive impact on the performance of the organization. But in Bangladesh the practice of corporate governance is not satisfactory level.

The banking industry is the nerve centre of the economy. The consequences of the destruction of this industry will largely affect other industry because they depend on the banking sector for their required funds. Although the entire schedule banks highly maintain the rules and regulation of Bangladesh Bank corresponding to Corporate Governance, banking industry in Bangladesh are at stake due to the fraud and corruption of board of directors. One of the reasons of corruption originates from the family ownership of bank controlling that means more directorial posts are captured by a single family. Other reasons are loopholes of rules and regulation, mismanagement and malpractices in the banking industry. Mahmood and Islam (2015) explained in their study that top management influence as well as political pressure in lending decisions creates fraud and corruption in the banking sector. This problem directly affects the performance of the banks. Recently banking sector of Bangladesh has been criticized because of their financial scams. According to CPD report the banking sector is struggling to recover from the setbacks of financial scams found in recent years. Mainly financial scams are created from loan. The banks do not recover the loans which they authorized to the unqualified and scrupulous borrower.

In 2012, the largest commercial bank 'Sonali Bank Ltd' corruption came in front of public. Between 2010 and 2012, it has disbursed loans of BDT 36.48 billion (US\$460 million) illegally. After that, corruptions of other banks are coming in front of public gradually. The increase in non-performing loans in both private and public sector of banking institutions is really worrying. According to Hossain (2015) a large amount of bad loans of TK.156.67 billion was written off during the last five years. According to Bangladesh Bank, loans of TK. 315 billion have been written off as of March 2014. Annual average amount of written-off loans stood at TK 30.66 billion during the last five years while it was about TK.

15.83 billion till 2009. In August 2014, the central bank unearthed TK. 36 billion loan scams in one of the country's largest banks, where loans are granted to a little-known business house without the minimum collateral required as security. The large amount of nonperforming loan affects the profitability of the bank. The present economically and financially undesirable situation in this sector demands effective corporate governance. It is hoped that effective corporate governance will bring down fraud and corruption in the banking industry. It is also hoped that corporate governance would have prevented such type of loan scams and would have saved the banking industry from incurring massive losses. Therefore this situation has led to the study of corporate governance principles to improve the performance of banking industry.

According to Klapper and Love (2004), Gompers, Ishii and Metrick (2003) corporate governance plays an important role in improving the value of the firm and there is a direct relationship between the two in both developing and developed countries. A study by Becht, Botton and Roell (2003) shows that corporate governance practices positively influences the profitability of the organization while Macavoy and Millstein (2003) found that board composition does not have any effect on financial performance.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

This study aims to investigate how corporate governance and financial performance are interrelated by including all the listed conventional commercial banks. To achieve this aim, the objective of the study is to examine whether different variables of board structure have any influence on the performance of banking industry in Bangladesh.

1.3. Significance of the Study

The study will contribute in the existing literature by identifying loopholes of rules and regulations related to corporate governance and help the policymaker, regulators to remove these loopholes. It also helps them to find out in what ways the banks can implement good corporate governance that aligns with bank performance.

1.4. Statement of Hypotheses

H₁: There is a statistically significant relationship between board size and financial performance.

H₂: There is a statistically significant relationship between board independent director and financial performance.

H₃: There is a statistically significant relationship between board audit committee and financial performance.

H₄: There is a statistically significant relationship between board chief executive officer duality and financial performance.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature on board structure and firm's performance especially four main board attributes- board size, board independent director, board audit committee, chief executive officer duality. The methodology of the study is proposed and described in section 3. Section 4 provides the results and discussion on statistical analysis from the collected data on different variables. Conclusions and decision implications are presented in section 5.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Corporate governance is a multi-faceted subject and essential factor of the organizations. Because it is not only the required condition for the proper growth of the firm in the market, but also the most valuable item for the shareholders in order to keep up with the impartiality, accountability, disclosure and transparency of the different elements and parameters. According to Cadbury (1992), corporate governance is the mechanism used to discipline organizations. Morin and Jarrell (2001) argue that corporate governance is a framework that controls and safeguards the interest of the relevant players in the market. The best corporate governance practices can improve overall accountability and performance throughout the organization.

Like many other developing economies, Bangladesh has been experiencing broad-based corporate governance reform initiatives since 2001 under the guidance and sponsorships of the International Financial Institutions (IFIs) such as the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, and the Asian Development Bank (Haque and Arun, 2016). Following this, the regulatory authority of Bangladesh introduces Code of Corporate Governance that prescribes the principles, procedures and processes of corporate governance practice. Many of the organizations in Bangladesh already have practices and procedures in keeping with the provisions of the Code. But the level of corporate governance practice is not sufficient. In fact, Bangladesh has lagged behind from its neighbors and the global economy. The reasons are most companies are family oriented and motivation to disclose information and improve governance practices by companies is felt negatively. According to Ahmad and Yusuf (2005) the reason of poor corporate governance practices in Bangladesh are poor bankruptcy laws, no push from the international investor community, limited or no disclosure regarding related party transactions, weak regulatory system, general meeting scenario, lack of shareholder active participations.

The worth of the organization is related to the performance of the organization and it is obvious that good corporate governance practices are essential in determining the worth. The observation of previous literature on corporate governance refers that the worth of the organization depends on the components of internal and micro environment i.e. roles of a regulatory authority, board, management, suppliers, customers and creditors of the organization.

The Board of directors of an organization is a key mechanism in a functioning corporate governance system. The board is not only responsible to monitor the behavior of the management but also is accountable to the stakeholders of the organization. Board size is important for ensuring good performance of the organization. Beiner et al. (2004 and 2006), Dalton et al. (1999), Dehaene, De Vuyst and Ooghe (2001) found a positive relationship between board size and company performance. Yermack (1996), Loderer and Peyer (2002), Mak and Kusnadi (2005), Haniffa and Hudaib (2006) found a significantly negative impact on firm performance. A large board size is thought to be less effective in case of major issues. But according to Goodstein et al. (1994), Pearce and Zahra (1992), Uadiale (2010) large board size is believed to be beneficial for firms to save its valuable resources and to decrease uncertainties. On the other hand, a small board size is considered to improve the performance of the firm. Lipton and Lorsch (1992) suggest an optimal board size between seven and nine directors. Yoshikawa and Phan (2003) also highlight that larger boards tend to be less cohesive and more difficult to coordinate because there might be a large number of potential interactions and conflicts among the group members. Mak and Kusnadi (2005) argue that small boards were more positively associated with high performance.

According to corporate governance principles the role of audit committee is important in improving the performance of firm. Securities and Exchange Commission rules (2012) audit committee should work independently and perform their duties with professional care. Audit committee is a monitoring mechanism that increases the quality of information. Klein (1998) and Anderson et al. (2004) reported a positive relationship between audit committee and firm's performances. On the other hand, Kajola (2008) shows there are no significant relationship between audit committee and firm's performance.

The agency theory recommends the involvement of independent non-executive directors to monitor any self-interested actions by managers and to minimize agency costs (Le, Walters and Kroll 2006; Williams et al. 2006). Although the executive directors have specialized skills, expertise and valuable knowledge of the firms' operating activities, there is a demand for the independent directors to contribute in the field of new ideas, independence, objectivity and expertise knowledge (Weir, 1997). According to Securities and Exchange Commission rules (2012) at least one fifth (1/5) of the total number of directors in the company's board shall be independent directors. The role independent director is to effectively monitor and control firm activities in reducing intentional managerial fraudulent activities. The proportion of independent directors is positively correlated to the firm's performance (Agrawal and Knoeber, 1996). Moreover, Rashid et al. (2010a), Kajola (2008), Klein (1998), Yermack (1996), Berkman et al. (2005), and Moscu (2013) concluded that the independent directors cannot add potential value to the firm's economic performance. It has been further argued that there is no relationship between the proportion of independent directors and superior firm performance (Hermalin and Weisbach, 1991). Increasing the level of the proportion of independent directors simultaneously increase firm performance as they are more effective monitors of managers (Mehran, 1995). Some researchers found that although the proportion of independent directors on the board is high, the level of board independent and professionalism is not necessarily good (Chen et al., 2007).

Securities and Exchange Commission rules (2012) explain that the positions of Chairman of the Board and CEO should be filled by different individuals since their functions are necessarily separate. Duality occurs when one individual holds the two most powerful posts of Chief Executive Officer (CEO) and Board chairman (Weir & Laing, 2001). The separation of the two positions creates necessary check and balances over their performance. The results of the study of Klein (2002) suggest that boards that are separated from the CEO are more effective in monitoring the corporate financial accounting process. Generally separation of board chair from CEO reduces agency costs for a firm (Coleman & Osei, 2007). Kajola (2008) found a positive and statistically significant relationship between performance and separation of board chair and CEO.

3. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

3.1. Selection of Sample Size

There are 57 scheduled banks in Bangladesh who operate under full control and supervision of Bangladesh Bank which is empowered to do so through Bangladesh Bank Order, 1972 and Bank Company Act, 1991. Among 57 scheduled banks six are state owned commercial banks (SOCBs), two specialized banks (SDBs), thirty two conventional private commercial banks (CPCBs), eight islamishariah based PCBs, nine foreign commercial banks (FCBs). The sample size was selected using the two-stage sampling method. In the first stage, 32 conventional banks were selected from 57 commercial banks. SOCBs, SDBs, islamishariah based PCB, FCBs have been kept outside the sample mainly because these banks operate in a different environment where rules and regulations are quite different from private

conventional banks. In the second stage 22 conventional banks were selected from 32 banks as sample on the basis of two criteria:

- The banks should be listed under the Dhaka Stock Exchange.
- They should complete 10 years of their operation.

3.2. Data Collection

The study has used secondary sources of information. Accounting information of related banks such as total assets, total equities and net income was collected from published annual reports. Other issues like total number of directors, number of outside independent directors, number of board audit committee members and CEO duality were also collected from the same sources.

3.3. Research Design and Data Analysis

The research design of the paper is used quantitative correlation method. In order to examine the relationship between corporate governance practices and banks performance the Karl Pearson correlation techniques and linear regression analysis were used. Furthermore mean, median, maximum, minimum, standard deviation, kurtosis, skewness were used for data analysis. The data analysis in this study was conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. The time horizon of data analysis was 5 years from 2012 to 2016.

3.4. Model Specification

In order to examine the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance, the following model was developed:

$$Y_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 BS + \beta_2 BID + \beta_3 BAC + \beta_4 CEO D + \varepsilon$$

Where $Y_{i,t}$, α , β_i , ε , BS, BID, BAC, CEO D represents alternatively ROA and ROE, intercept, regression coefficient, error term, Board Size, Board Independent director, Board Audit Committee, Chief Executive Officer Duality respectively. The subscript i represents the different banks and t represents the different years.

3.5. Description of Variables

In the study, two different dependent variables were adopted to measure firm's financial performance. One was Return on Asset (ROA)-calculated as "Earnings before Interest and Taxes" (EBIT) scaled by the book value of total assets and another was Return on Equity (ROE)-calculated as "Earnings before Interest and Taxes" (EBIT) scaled by total Equity.

Based on the existing relevant empirical studies, the independent variables for this study were selected as board size, board independent director, board audit committee and chief executive officer duality. Board size represents the total number of directors on the board, Board Independent director represents the proportion of independent director on the board, Board Audit Committee represents the total number of members in the committee and Chief Executive officer Duality means board chairman and CEO are same individual. Value zero (0) for if the different individual occupies the post of the board chairman and the CEO and one (1) for otherwise.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

Statistical Techniques Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Board Size	110	7	20	13.30	14	3.57	.069	-.472
Board Independent Director	110	0	6	2.23	2	.95	.325	2.143
Board Audit Committee	110	3	6	4.31	4.5	.84	-.360	-1.029
CEO Officer Duality	110	0	0	.00	0	.00	.	.
Return on Asset	110	0.21	1.90	1.06	1.03	.37	.210	-.139
Return on Equity	110	3.02	23.40	12.12	11.88	3.98	.188	-.170

Corporate governance plays a vital role on firm's activity, longevity and far reaching pressurize on its overall life. Moreover, as far as globalization arriving and involving our door to door, economy is changing from person to firm, firm to institution and also on global wide. On our study, we asses 5 years data of 22 banks, where our study variables are Board size, Independency of Director, size of the Board Audit Committee members, duality hoax of CEO, Return on Asset (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). The descriptive statistics of all the variables used in the study are shown in above table. As shown in table, average firm performance is 1.06% ranging from 0.21% to 1.90% under ROA performance measure and 12.12% ranging from 3.02% to 23.40% under the ROE performance measure. It indicates that for every BDT 100 invested as asset, there is a return of BDT 1.06 and for every BDT 100 invested as equity, there is a return is BDT 12.12. On our study, the average board size is 13.30 and the member ranges from 7 to 20. The standard deviation of board size is 3.57. It indicates that the board size 10 to 16 is preferable. The average number of board independent director is 2.23, ranging from 0 to 6. It indicates that minimum number of BID is not maintained sometimes. According to BSEC CG notification, At least one fifth (1/5) of the total number of directors in the company's board shall be independent directors. On scrutinizing overall branches, their situations etc. an active and efficient audit team is a must. Average size of board audit committee is 4.31 ranging from 3 to 6. According to BSEC CG notification, the Audit Committee shall be composed of at least 3 (three) members. It indicates that number of board audit committee member is maintained properly. But it is necessary to focus that the Board of Directors shall appoint members of the Audit Committee who shall be directors of the company and shall include at least 1 (one) independent director (BSEC CG condition no 3.1(ii)) and The Board of Directors shall select 1 (one) member of the Audit Committee to be Chairman of the Audit Committee who shall be an independent director (BSEC CG condition no 3.2 (i)), so we can conclude that these two conditions are not followed when number of independent director was 0. CEO duality is 0 for all selected banks. It indicates that the Chairman of the board and CEO of the organization is not same person. According to BSEC CG Condition no. 1.4, the positions of the Chairman of the Board and the Chief Executive Officer of the companies shall be filled by different individuals. It means that all banks followed this condition. From the skewness result, we find that all variables are fairly symmetrical i.e. distribution is normal. Except BID, kurtosis of other variables is negative which indicates that variables have a flatter distribution but BID has peaked distribution.

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Table 2 Pearson Correlation – ROA& ROE as a value of Firm (N=110)

	Return on Asset	Return on Equity	Board Size	Board Independent Director	Board Audit Committee
Return on Asset	1	.685**	.037	.079	-.041
Return on Equity	.685**	1	-.156	.201*	-.155
Board Size	.037	-.156	1	.200*	.426**
Board Independent Director	.079	.201*	.200*	1	-.181
Board Audit Committee	-.041	-.155	.426**	-.181	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

On correlation analysis, our attempt is to find out the direction of relationship of several variables. Pearson correlation analysis is conducted on the variables. The results are shown in above table. ROA is positively correlated with board size and board independent director though this relationship is not significant. ROA is negatively correlated with board audit committee which is not significant too. On the other hand, ROE has a negative correlation with board size and board audit committee which is not significant but ROE is positively correlated with board independent director at 5% level of significance. Board size and board independent directors, board size and board audit committee are positively correlated at 5% and 1% level of significance respectively. However, correlation between CEO Duality and other variable can't be computed as CEO duality is zero for all.

Table 3 Linear Regression Results (N-110)

Variables	ROA				ROE			
	Beta Coefficient	t-value	Standard Error	P Value	Beta Coefficient	t-value	Standard Error	P Value
Constant	1.040	4.666	.223	.000	13.392	5.801	2.308	.000
BS	.005	.413	.012	.680	-.210	-1.743	.121	.084
BID	.024	.583	.041	.561	.982	2.338	.420	.021
BAC	-.022	-.445	.049	.657	-.152	-.299	.510	.766
R Square: .009 Adjusted R Square: -.020 F: .304 F significance: .823 Durbin-Watson: 1.201					R Square: .081 Adjusted R Square: .055 F: 3.125 F significance: .029 Durbin-Watson: 1.318			

From the above result, the regression equation is written as

$$\text{ROA} = 1.040 + .005 \text{ BS} + .024 \text{ BID} - .022 \text{ BAC}$$

$$\text{ROE} = 13.392 - .210 \text{ BS} + .982 \text{ BID} - .152 \text{ BAC}$$

Regression enables us to understand how well and more crystal relationship is maintained through our model. Also, it helps us to assess whether the causes and effects are acting on which direction and how much the degree of effectiveness work.

If the effects of other variables are constant, then the ROA & ROE will come 1.040 units & 13.392 units respectively (significant at 1 percent level of significance). For each unit increase in board size, the ROA will increase .005 units and the return to equity will decrease .21 units. For each unit increase in board independent director, the ROA will increase .024 units & ROE will increase .982 units (which is significant at 5% level of significance). For

each unit increase in board audit committee, the ROA & REO will decrease .022 unit & .152unit.

R square value (also called the coefficient of determination) which is the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables. Our value is .009 and .081 that means our independent variables explain .9% and 8.1% of the variability of our dependent variable. The adjusted R square value indicates the explanatory power of the independent variables which is -.020 and 0.055 respectively for ROA and ROE. It indicates that -2% of the variation in ROA and 5.5% of the variation in ROE is explained by the variation in the independent variables. This means that it doesn't effectively account the changes in profitability and can't be used as a sound decision making tool. F statistics is used to testing the overall significance of model result. The F statistics is .304 and 3.125 for ROA and ROE respectively. From the result of the analysis, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) generates a p-value of 0.823 and 0.029 for ROA and ROE respectively; indicating model is significant for ROE. This shows that the explanatory variables are linearly related to ROE of firm's performance and the model seems to have some validity. For the models with dependent variable ROA & ROE, CEO Duality is constant and therefore deleted from the analysis. The D. W. 1.201 & 1.318 statistics indicates the presence of auto-correlation since it is below the rule of Thumb of 2.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Corporate governance is the topic widely discussed in today's world. Most of the researchers in this field have concentrated on the compliance status of CG in the organization. The present study aims at investigating the influence of corporate governance mechanisms on the performance of the firms performing in the banking industry of Bangladesh. This study examines the relationship that exists between four corporate governance mechanisms (board size, board independent director, board audit committee, chief executive officer duality) and firm performance, using two proxies, (ROA and ROE) to test the hypotheses proposed in this study. The result indicates that hypothesis one (H_1) is rejected. There is positive but not significant relationship of board size with ROA. On the other hand, board size is negatively correlated with ROE which is not significant too. It implies that there are information asymmetries between BOD and management. As a principal agent to take care and get involved in fundamental important decision of the bank, the board of directors works closely with a management in a cooperative relationship of trust for sustainable development. Banks and regulatory authorities should monitor board structure, family ownership, board composition, rules and regulation of appointment, duties and power closely. Initiative to reduce information asymmetries between BOD and management will improve financial performance of banks. Hypothesis two (H_2) has a mixed result. Board independent director has a positive relationship with ROA and positive significant relationship with ROE. Therefore, it is supportive that outside independent directors of banks are able to ensure the checks and balances of accountability and management activities. The proportion of independent directors in board is only 16.77% on average; indicating that required number of BID i.e. 1/5 or 20% is not fulfilled and they certainly have little influence in firm's performance. A board consist of majority inside directors have no significant relationship with firm's financial performance. As Board Independent Directors have significant positive influence, bank should give more concentration to increase the proportion and importance of independent director in the board. There is a negative relationship of board audit committee with ROA and ROE. It implies that hypothesis three (H_3) rejected. Though this relationship is not significant, it implies that board audit committee can't add potential economic value to the banks in Bangladesh. But BAC is important to review reports on fraud and forgery surfaced

among others. It ensures whether complete and true information is reflected in financial statements and BB guidelines are followed in making such statements. Therefore, importance of board audit committee can't be overlooked. Rule regarding CEO Officer Duality is followed by all banks in last 5 years. Moreover, confirming the situation, descriptive statistics also shows that for the sampled firm, financial performance is not good.

Therefore, this study recommends that representative board size and board audit committee for banks of Bangladesh as board of directors and board audit committee are supposed to monitor the activities to increase firm performance and enhance the representation of independent director on the board will improve the financial performance of banks. From a policy perspective, we believe the findings of this study can be helpful for users to improve financial performances through effective practice of corporate governance.

This study may be improved by including some other variables that may affect bank's performance. This study could be further extended to other types of bank and a comparative analysis could be performed between private conventional banking and other types of banks (Islami Shariah based PCB, FCB, SOCB).

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